

Harmonic Generation from Vanillylideneaniline: An Organic Non Linear Optical Material

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Abstract

Single crystals of 2-methoxy-4(phenyliminomethyl)phenol were grown from ethanol by slow evaporation solution growth technique. Crystallization in orthorhombic crystal system with non-centrosymmetric space group C222₁ was confirmed by single crystal x-ray diffraction analysis. Preliminary screening of non linear optical activity has been carried out by Kurtz-Perry technique. Computational studies to deduce the favored HOMO-LUMO band gap for non linear optical activity, molecular electrostatic potential and first order hyperpolarizability of the molecule were executed using Gaussian 09 programme. Natural population analysis visualizes the charge distribution in an isolated molecule. By means of measuring third order non linearity using Z-scan, it is proposed that the material can be used for reverse saturable absorption.

Keywords: Crystal growth, Non linear optics, Second harmonic generation, Organic materials,

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